

Electronic Spectra of Some Optically Active Strychnine Benzoates

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of strychnine benzoate and strychnine (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) chloro- and bromo benzoates have been studied in the solvent chloroform and methanol. The study in the solvent chloroform has been done with a view to comparing 'characteristic' wavelengths (λ_0 , s), deduced from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation, with absorption maxima (λ_{max}) obtained by direct measurement. The differences between λ_0 and λ_{max} range from 3.0 nm to 147.6 nm. An explanation of this discrepancy has been given. A detailed study of the spectra in the solvent methanol has been undertaken with a view to study the effect of polar solvent and the substituent groups on the U.V. spectra of these compounds.

The rotatory dispersion of optically active compounds is generally expressible by Drude's equation, namely,

$$[\alpha] = \Sigma \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2},$$

where $[\alpha]$ is specific rotation for wavelength λ , and K and λ_0 are constants. According to Kuhn¹ the 'characteristic' wavelengths (λ_0 , s) obtained from a study of rotatory dispersion in a region away from absorption are intimately connected with absorption bands which are chiefly responsible for optical rotatory power. A close agreement between the 'characteristic' wavelengths (λ_0 , s) deduced from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation and the absorption maxima (λ_{max}) as obtained by direct measurement was observed by Lowry and co-workers^{2,3} in case of camphor quinone and by Pickard and Hunter⁴ in case of d-v-nonyl nitrite. Singh and co-workers⁵ have reported good agreement between λ_0 and λ_{max} in the case of camphor- β -sulphonates of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloro and bromo anilines and camphor- β -sulphonyl (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) bromo phenylamides, methyl camphor- β -sulphonate and its ketimines. In the case of *p*-sulphonamide, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methoxy phenylimino camphors and camphor- β -sulphonyl-methoxy (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) and ethoxy (*m*- and *p*-) phenylamide in methyl alcohol and some camphor-quinoxalines, however, they have reported^{6,7} that λ_0 do not agree with the λ_{max} value.

In the present study the U.V. absorption spectra of strychnine benzoate and strychnine (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) chloro and bromo benzoates has been undertaken with a view to compare the characteristic wavelengths, λ_0 , s , obtained from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation, with those obtained from direct absorption measurements. The effect of polar solvents and the substituent groups on the absorption spectra, has also been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Compounds were prepared and purified as described by Pant⁸. The absorption spectra were recorded in very dilute solutions of the compounds in spectroscopically pure solvents, with Hitachi Perkin-Elmer Model No. 139-UV-VIS-spectrophotometer. The molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , were calculated from observed values of absorption at different wavelengths but their peak values, ϵ_{max} , corresponding to the absorption maxima, λ_{max} , only have been recorded in Table 1. The absorption curves of these compounds were obtained by plotting the molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , against the corresponding wavelength, λ , and are given in figs 1-4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Relation between optical activity and absorption spectra of strychnine benzoates

The rotatory dispersion equation of Drude

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^t = \sum \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$$

contains several terms in summation, $K'/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0'^2$, $K''/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0''^2$, ..., giving the characteristic wavelengths λ_0' , λ_0'' , ..., which govern the rotation of the compound. The rotatory dispersion curves can, however, be represented by a very few Drude terms⁹. In the case of

FIG 1

'simple' dispersion, one term of Drude's equation is required which means that there is one characteristic wavelength which corresponds to the absorption maximum, of the absorption

TABLE I

Comparison of absorption maxima with the characteristic wavelengths

Solvent—Chloroform

Concentration = 0.0001M

S. No.	Compounds	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ_{max}	λ_0^p from Drude's one term equation $[\alpha]_0 = K/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2$ (nm)	Difference $\lambda_0 - \lambda_{max}$ (nm)
1.	Strychnine-Benzoate	256	14,500		
		281	5,400	295.2	5.2
		290	3,600		
2.	Strychnine- <i>o</i> -chloro benzoate	255	13,000		
		280	3,700	220.7	34.3
		290	2,800		
3.	Strychnine- <i>m</i> -chloro benzoate	256	13,600		
		281	5,200	299.3	9.3
		290	4,000		
4.	Strychnine- <i>p</i> -chloro benzoate	245	23,300		
		280	4,700	437.6	147.6
		290	3,450		
5.	Strychnine- <i>o</i> -bromo benzoate	256	12,600		
		281	4,800	288.0	3.0
		291	3,300		
6.	Strychnine- <i>m</i> -bromo benzoate	256	13,350		
		280	5,100	—	—
		290	3,900		
7.	Strychnine- <i>p</i> -bromo benzoate	247	27,200		
		281	5,400	232.8	14.2
		290	3,800		

Relation between chemical constitution and ultra-violet absorption spectra of strychnine benzoates : In order to provide a basis for the elucidation of the relationship of U.V. absorption spectra to molecular structure in these compounds, their spectra was determined in methanol, whereby the measurements could be recorded up to the region near 200 nm. The effect of solvent polarity on the spectra is observed on comparing the results obtained in chloroform and methanol (Tables I and II).

(a) *Effect of solvent polarity on the absorption spectra of strychnine benzoates* : The influence of the polarity of the solvent is more distinctly brought out if a comparison is

made between λ_{max} values and the dielectric constants of the two solvents. The decreasing order of the dielectric constants of methanol and chloroform runs as follows :

Methanol (34.7) > Chloroform (5.06). All the bands in chloroform undergo a blue shift as the polarity of the solvent is increased. The blue shift arises due to the formation of hydrogen—bonding which will increase the energy of excitation. Thus all the compounds show a hypsochromic shift when the solvent is changed from chloroform to methanol. It is also noted that the intensity of absorption decreases with increasing polarity of the solvent.

TABLE II

Comparison of absorption spectra of strychnine benzoates

Sl. No.	Compounds	Solvent—Methanol							
		A Band		B Band		C Bands			
		λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ_{max}						
1.	Strychnine-benzoate	208	30,400	253.5	13,700	279	4,700	289	3,300
2.	Strychnine- <i>o</i> -chlorobenzoate	208	34,600	253.0	10,700	278	4,000	288	2,950
3.	Strychnine- <i>m</i> -chlorobenzoate	207	38,000	253.5	13,200	278	4,800	288	3,600
4.	Strychnine- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzoate	206	32,400	237.0	20,550	279	4,350	289	3,100
5.	Strychnine- <i>o</i> -bromobenzoate	207	35,200	252.0	10,200	279	3,900	288	2,700
6.	Strychnine- <i>m</i> -bromobenzoate	208	38,000	253.0	12,900	278	4,400	289	3,350
7.	Strychnine- <i>p</i> -bromobenzoate	205	34,400	243.5	23,050	279	4,200	289	2,900

(b) *Effect of substitution on the absorption spectra of strychnine benzoates* : Strychnine exhibits maxima¹² at the following wavelengths in ethanol : 255 nm ($\epsilon = 12,590$), 280 nm ($\epsilon = 4,266$), and 290 nm ($\epsilon = 3,388$). Benzoic acid¹³ has been shown to have maxima in ethanol at 202 nm ($\epsilon = 7,943$), 228 nm ($\epsilon = 10,000$), 270 nm ($\epsilon = 758.6$) and 279 nm ($\epsilon = 549.5$). In the present study, strychnine benzoate and substituted strychnine benzoates exhibit four bands each in methanol. Strychnine benzoate (Table II) shows maxima at the following wavelengths : 208 nm ($\epsilon = 30,400$), 253.5 nm ($\epsilon = 13,700$), 279 nm ($\epsilon = 4,700$) and 289 nm ($\epsilon = 3,300$). For the purpose of discussion, the band at 208 nm will be labelled the A band, that at 253.5 nm the B band and the other two peaks the C band.

The very intense band at A is probably due to the benzenoid absorption, which has been obtained by the displacement of the band in benzene that occurs near 187.0 nm. The B and C bands have also been assumed to arise by the displacement of the bands of benzene occurring near 203.5 nm and 254.0 nm that has been brought about by substitution of the benzene ring in the benzoic acid part of the molecule. The R band ($n-\pi^*$), due to ketonic group in the strychnine part of the molecule, is probably submerged by the more intense C bands.

In the ortho-substituted compounds it is seen that the A and C bands of strychnine benzoate remains essentially unchanged in frequency, whereas the B band is displaced to shorter wavelengths. The intensities of B and C bands in these compounds is dependent upon the nature of the substituted group and its position in the ring. The shift of λ_{max} to shorter wavelength is accompanied by a decrease in intensity in the order : Cl(ortho) > Br (ortho). The decrease in intensity is in agreement with the size of Cl and Br (Vander waals Radius : Cl = 1.8; Br = 1.95). Thus steric inhibition of resonance was observed in the ortho-substituted benzoates. Now according to the theory of steric inhibition of resonance the structural change that results in going from strychnine benzoate to the para-substituted compound increases the conjugation, and, as pointed out by Braude¹⁴, decreases the energy of excitation thus resulting in a bathochromic shift of this band. On the basis of resonance considerations alone, the position of the B band in the corresponding ortho- and para-compounds should be nearly same. It is, however, observed that the B bands of the ortho-substituted compounds are displaced to longer wavelengths, when compared with the corresponding para-substituted compound. The C band, on the other hand, remains essentially unchanged in frequency of absorption.

In the *m*-substituted compounds there is considerable similarity of the spectra as compared to the corresponding ortho-substituted compounds. This kind of similarity has also been observed in the case of a large number of ortho- and meta-substituted benzenoid compounds by Doub and Vandenbelt¹⁵.

The spectra of *p*-substituted compounds shows that again the A and C bands of strychnine benzoate remain essentially constant in frequency of absorption, whereas the B band undergoes a considerable hypsochromic shift. The amounts of shift for the substituents being in the order : Cl > Br. The B band of both strychnine-*p*-chloro and *p*-bromo

benzoates are more intense than the strychnine benzoate. The order of decrease in intensity being : Br > Cl. The increase in absorption intensity of the para-substituted benzoates, over that of the unsubstituted ortho and meta-substituted strychnine benzoates may be attributed to the effect of para-substitution in promoting the ionic state and coplanar configuration¹⁶.

As pointed out above the B bands of ortho-substituted compounds are displaced to longer wavelengths, when compared with the corresponding *p*-substituted compound. This result is not in agreement with the expectations based on the inductive and resonance effects. This can, however, be explained on the basis of an electron-repelling π -inductive effect proposed by Clarke, Murrell and Tedder^{7,18}. According to their hypothesis for an electronegative substituent with an unshared pair, the properties which would be expected to depend markedly on distribution of the σ electrons, such groups would have a net inductive effect of electron withdrawal but for properties dependent primarily on the π -electrons, such as energies of $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions, the net inductive effect would be an electron-repelling one. On this basis the electronic transition energy will increase and accordingly a hypsochromic effect will take place.

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